

SOME ASPECTS OF THE STUDY OF SCIENTIFIC STYLE BY PHILOLOGY STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article discusses the issues of studying scientific speech by students of philology, emphasizes the need for students to develop skills of fluency in the scientific language in written and oral form. The author focuses on the features of the scientific style, the assimilation of which will help to effectively master the language of science.

Keywords: scientific style, students of philology, stylistic features, qualities of scientific speech.

The conditions of development of science as a social phenomenon and the traditions and norms of scientific communication dictated by this have determined the targeted selection and organization of linguistic means in the sphere of scientific communication, their special use. The consequence of this was the formation of a scientific functional style, possessing a number of essential and stable features, which practically does not cause objections from linguists.

But even a non-linguist dealing with various types of scientific literature often intuitively feels that it contains “something very persistently distinctive, preserved in the ‘fabric’ of scientific works” [4, p. 14]. Therefore, considering scientific style from the theoretical standpoint of functional stylistics, in our opinion, the main methodological goal in teaching Russian stylistics to philology students is to develop their skills in identifying, analyzing, and, most importantly, using for practical purposes these “persistently distinctive” linguistic and constructive features, “representing a certain integral complex” [3, p. 129].

Let's consider the stylistic features of scientific text.

Science is characterized by an intellectual and conceptual way of thinking, a desire for the most generalized, objective, impersonal knowledge, and the recording of data using its own language – precise, capacious, laconic and expressive.

Of course, these qualities are not specific to scientific speech alone. They are necessary for business language and journalistic language, and are desirable in colloquial speech. However, in the scientific style, these speech qualities are a

requirement of science itself: without them, a scientific work cannot exist. The above-mentioned speech qualities are manifested in interconnection and often against the background of specific, purely scientific constructive features, such as, for example, abstractness, compression, terminology, unambiguity, isolation, etc. The main features of scientific speech, reflecting theoretical thinking, are logic and generality. These features are determined by the features of science as a type of activity aimed at systematizing human knowledge about the world, identifying general patterns and proving their truth [2, p. 93].

Thus, logic is a communicative quality that presupposes the ability to consistently, non-contradictorily and reasonably formulate the expressed content. It follows from this that a text will be logical if its conclusions follow from the content, they are not contradictory, and the text itself is divided into separate semantic segments that reflect the movement of thought from the particular to the general or from the general to the particular.

Logic characterizes the structure of speech, its organization and evaluates the semantic links of linguistic units in speech from the point of view of the laws of logic and correct thinking. These links are recognized as logically consistent if they correspond to the connections and relationships of reality and correctly reflect the structure of thought. Therefore, we can talk about two types of logic: subject and conceptual.

Subject logic consists in the correspondence of semantic connections and relations of language units in speech to the connections and relations of objects and phenomena in reality. Conceptual logic is an adequate reflection of the structure of thought and its development in the semantic connections of speech components. Subject and conceptual logic are interconnected and in a scientific text usually appear as a unity.

Scientific style has a large arsenal of means of connecting independent sentences and individual informative parts of the text. Among them are special means (words, phrases and sentences) indicating the sequence of development of thoughts (in the beginning, then, then, first of all, preliminary, etc.), the connection of previous and subsequent information (as indicated, as already said, as noted, considered, etc.), cause-and-effect relationships (but, therefore, due to this, therefore, in connection with the fact that, etc.), the transition to a new topic (let us now consider, let us move on to consideration, etc.), the result, conclusion (so, in this way, in conclusion, from this point of view, etc.), the proximity, identity of objects, circumstances, features (he, the same, such, so, here, etc.).

Clarity as the quality of scientific speech presupposes comprehensibility and accessibility. Therefore, scientific, scientific-educational and popular scientific texts differ both in the selection of material and in the method of its linguistic design.

Another quality of scientific speech – precision – presupposes unambiguous understanding, the absence of discrepancies between the signified and the signifier. Therefore, in scientific texts proper, as a rule, there are no figurative, expressive means; words are used mainly in their direct meaning.

The strict requirements of accuracy imposed on scientific texts make it almost impossible to use figurative language devices in them – metaphors, epithets, artistic comparisons, proverbs, etc. However, such devices can penetrate into scientific works, since the scientific style strives not only for accuracy, but also for persuasiveness and evidence. Figurative devices are also necessary in many cases to implement the requirement of clarity and intelligibility of presentation, which R.A. Budagov has repeatedly emphasized: “... imagery often penetrates the style of a scientific work and is widely used for the purposes of clarity and persuasiveness in purely logical argumentation” [1, p. 40].

Due to their low frequency, figurative means in scientific texts are unpredictable and always unexpected. Therefore, they make a strong impression on the reader or listener, as they activate not only intellectual and conceptual, but also figurative thinking. These qualities are especially necessary for popular science and scientific and educational works, therefore, it is in these texts that figurative means are used especially often.

Emotionality, like expressiveness, in the scientific style, which requires an objective presentation of scientific data, is expressed differently than in other styles. Although the presentation of scientific facts and discoveries presupposes a strictly neutral tone, the author of the work does not always renounce an emotional-evaluative attitude to the events and facts presented. In the most significant parts of the text, in terms of meaning, such linguistic means may appear that openly express the author's attitude, the author's emotions.

Scientific text is characterized by the so-called limited authorial, personal element. This is expressed in the reduced use of the pronoun I and the corresponding personal forms of the verb. When it is necessary to name the speaker in a scientific text, the first person plural we, the word author, impersonal constructions, indefinite-personal, impersonal sentences, passive phrases, etc. are usually used.

The desire for limited use of the author's self is not only a tribute to etiquette, but also a manifestation of an abstract-generalized stylistic feature of scientific

speech, reflecting the form of thinking. The abstract-generalized, abstracted nature of thinking is manifested in scientific speech at the lexical, morphological and syntactic levels. For example, in vocabulary - the widespread use of words with abstract meaning, in morphology - the elimination of the specific tense of the verb, in syntax - the use of impersonal and indefinite-personal sentences, passive phrases, etc.

The supra-individual character of scientific speech is also connected with the tendency toward standardization. This tendency manifests itself both in relation to the structure of the entire text and to the use of linguistic means in it.

Standards are a neutral stylistic category. Being ready-made speech forms, correlated with a certain situation, they significantly facilitate communication and are convenient for use in scientific communication. Therefore, many types of descriptive texts are built according to an established strict standard, which is not recommended to deviate from.

Standardization of text structure is also supported by standardization of language design. The higher the requirements of the standard and composition, the more often language standards are used.

Scientific style reflects the features of scientific knowledge and scientific thinking. In our opinion, consideration of the qualitative characteristics of scientific prose will allow the most effective work on the correct definition by students of the stylistic organization of the text, its speech profile in the aspect of functional-speech differentiation; correct structuring of the text, knowing the principles of its construction, using stylistically correct means and observing the features of the genre.

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